

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
SUSPICIOUS EMAIL DETECTION SYSTEM
PROJECT
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SUSPICIOUS EMAIL DETECTION

Abstract

The aim of this project is to suspect the E-mails which consist of offensive, anti-social elements and block them which helps in identifying the suspicious user.

In this project, suspicious users are identified by determining the keywords used by him/her. The keywords such as bomb, RDX. are found in the mails which are sent by the user. All these blocked mails are checked by the administrator and identify the users who sent such mails.

This is very useful in real-time scenario in which you can resume the anti-social activities.

It consists 5 modules:

Modules in the Suspicious E-mail detection

- **Login Module**
- **Registration Module**
- **Administration Module**
- **User Module**
- **Mailing Module**

1) **Login Module:**

This module is used by administrator and users (who are authenticated) to login into the secure mail. The login details of the specified person will be entered and hence can enter into the secure mail.

2) **Registration Module:**

This module is used by the unauthenticated users who are unregistered. The users must register themselves such that they can login into the secure mail.

3) **Administration Module:**

This module is used by the administrator to perform the functions like managing the keywords, entering new keywords and to check out the block list of the discarded mails.

4) **User Module:**

This module is used by the users to do operations like composing mail, checking out the mails in inbox and finally sending the mails to the authenticated users by attaching a message.

5) **Mailing Module:**

This module is used by the users perform mailing system. The mailing system consists of composing the mails, sending the mails and checking out the mails in inbox.

1. INTRODUCTION:

1.2 About the project

Suspicious email detection is a kind of mailing system where suspicious users are identified by determining the keywords used by him/her. The keywords such as bomb,RDX., are found in the mails which are sent by the user. All these blocked mails are checked by the administrator and identify the users who sent such mails.

This is very useful in real-time scenario in which you can resume the anti-social activities.It consists 5 modules:

The users of this system are compose mails to the other users who are authenticated already. If the composed mails consist of the keywords such as bomb, RDX, Terrorist etc. These suspected mails are blocked or discarded by the administrator so that they cannot be forwarded. This system is designed such a way that the users can easily interact with the system with minimum knowledge to browse the internet.

The Second chapter explains the exact Definition of the Problem and evolves out with the Feasibility Study of the product/part.

The Third chapter is System Analysis which deals about the Hardware and Software Specifications, and Software Requirement Specification, under this SRS Formal Description and Module Description.

The Fourth chapter describes the System Design, under this two levels of designs, they are

- High level design (Data design, functional & interface design).
- Low level design (Pseudo code & detail description of functions).

The Fifth chapter fully deals about Testing and Implementation of the whole project.

The Sixth chapter deals the Conclusion and Foreseeable Enhancements of the system.

The Seventh chapter deals about the Bibliography of this Project.

The Eight chapter is the final one which deals about the language used, tools used, Screen layouts and Reports

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS

2.1 Definition of the problem

To create or develop a new system first we have to study the prior system, Analysis difficult problems faced by the operator of that system. System Analysis therefore understands such problems and proposes a new system in which the above problems are rectified.

Existing system

In the existing system, the mails are sent to the authenticated users who are intended to be received.

Some defects in existing system are:

- Suspicious mails cannot be detected.
- Offensive users cannot be identified.

Proposed System

In the proposed system the suspicious users are detected and the offensive mails are blocked.

Features of proposed system:

- This helps in finding out anti social elements.
- This provides the security to system which adapts it.
- This also helps the intelligence bureau, crime branch etc.,

Module Description:

The proposed system is developed by using five modules:

- **Login Module**
- **Registration Module**

- **Administration Module**
- **User Module**
- **Mailing Module**

Login Module:

This module is used by administrator and users (who are authenticated) to login into the secure mail. The login details of the specified person will be entered and hence can enter into the secure mail.

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This module is used by the unauthenticated users who are unregistered. The users must register themselves such that they can login into the secure mail.

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This module is used by the administrator to perform the functions like managing the keywords, entering new keywords and to check out the block list of the discarded mails.

User Module:

This module is used by the users to do operations like composing mail, checking out the mails in inbox and finally sending the mails to the authenticated users by attaching a message.

Mailing Module:

This module is used by the users perform mailing system. The mailing system consists of composing the mails, sending the mails and checking out the mails in inbox.

Module connectivity:

In the administrator module the administrator will be responsible for blocking the mails and managing the keywords.

In the client module, different clients who are registered can compose the mails and can send the mails to the registered users only.

2.2 Feasibility study

It is necessary and prudent to evaluate the feasibility of a project at the earliest possible time. There may be different ways of checking whether a system is feasible or not. The following feasibility studies were performed to gauge the feasibility of the system.

2.2.1 Operational Feasibility

In this test, the operational scope of the system is checked. The system under consideration should have enough operational reach. It is observed that the proposed system is very user friendly and since the system is built with enough help, even persons with little knowledge of windows can find the system very easy.

2.2.2 Technical Feasibility

This test includes a study of function, performance and constraints that may affect the ability to achieve an acceptable system. This test begins with an assessment of the technical viability of the proposed system. One of the main fusers to be accessed is the need of various kinds of resources for the successful implementation for the proposed system.

2.2.3 Economical Feasibility

An evaluation of development cost weighed against the ultimate income or benefit derived from the development of the proposed system is made. Care must be taken that incurred in the development of the proposed of the system should not exceed from the system. The income can be in terms of money or goodwill, since the software brings in both, the system is highly viable.

3. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 Hardware and Software Specifications

The development of this project deals with the following environment

- Hardware requirements
- Software requirements

Hardware Requirements:

The selection of hardware is very important in the existence and proper working of any software. In the selection of hardware, the size and the capacity requirements are also important.

The suspicious email detection can be efficiently run on Pentium system with at least 128 MB RAM and Hard disk drive having 20 GB. Floppy disk drive of 1.44 MB and 14 inch Samsung color monitor suits the information system operation.(A Printer is required for hard copy output).

- Pentium processor ----- 233 MHZ or above
- RAM Capacity ----- 256MB
- Hard Disk ----- 20GB

Software Requirements:

One of the most difficult tasks is that, the selection of the software, once system requirement is known is determining whether a particular software package fits the requirements. After initial selection further security is needed to determine the desirability of particular software compared with other candidates. This section first summarizes the application requirement question and then suggests more detailed comparisons.

- Operating System :: Windows NT/2000
- Server Side :: JSP with Tomcat Server
- Client Side :: HTML ,JavaScript
- Services :: JDBC
- Database :: Oracle 10g/XE
- Integrated Development Environment :: My Eclipse 6.0

3.Fields Specification

Administrator: login name, password, login type.

User: user name, password.

3.2.1 Formal Description

Module Description

The main modules of this “suspicious email detection” are broadly divided into five. They are

- **Login Module**
- **Registration Module**
- **Administration Module**
- **User Module**
- **Mailing Module**

Login Module:

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4. SYSTEM DESIGN

Design Description:

Design is essentially a blue print or it acts as a bridge between the requirement specification and the final solution for satisfying the requirements.

Based on the work-flow described above we can draw the following conclusions for the Software System that has to be developed:

- The System needs to be a web-based system so that it allows the admin & clients to access the secure mail over the Internet.
- Being a web-based system, it enables the users to send e-mails to other users who are already registered. An added advantage is since the e-mail is delivered instantly, there could be instant responses from the admin if any suspicious emails are detected.
- The whole process depends on communications between admin & the users. If all these communications are done through a web-based system, then the time period for the whole process can be considerably brought down.
- The System needs to store the details of all the users.
- The System needs to store the details of all the information (sent mails, composed mails etc) held by all the users.
- The System needs to store the details of all the requirements held by the different users.
- Since it is a web-based system, a Login authorization should be provided so that Admin and users will be able to lookup & use options that are specific to them.
- The System should allow the users to enter their details.
- The System should provide an option to generate an user Report.
- The System should provide an option to generate block mails Report.
- The System should provide an option to generate selected users Report.

4.1 High level design

Data design

Table Name: Users

Description: This table is used to maintain the registered users information.

SL.NO	FIELD NAME	DATA TYPE	DESCRIPTION
1	USERNAME	Varchar2(10)	This is unique identifier given to an user to identify him uniquely. This is the Primary Key of the table.
2	PASSWORD	Varchar2(20)	This the password of the user

Table Name: block list

Description: This table is used for client's mailing information.

SL.NO	FIELD NAME	DATA TYPE	DESCRIPTION
1	MAIL TO	Varchar2(10)	To whom the user wants to send the mails
2	MAIL FROM	Varchar2(20)	From whom the users got the mails.
3	SUBJECT	Varchar2(40)	The subject present in the mail.
4	MESSAGE	Varchar2(40)	The message or the data present in the mail.

Table Name: keywords

Description: This table consists of the keywords of the mailing system.

SL.NO	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION
1	keyword	The suspected keywords of the mails.

OVERVIEW OF JAVA TECHNOLOGY

HISTORY OF JAVA

Java language was developed by James Gosling and his team at sun micro systems and released formally in 1995. Its former name is oak. Java Development Kit 1.0 was released in 1996. to popularize java and is freely available on Internet.

Overview of Java

Java is loosely based on C++ syntax, and is meant to be Object-Oriented Structure of java is midway between an interpreted and a compiled language . java programs are compiled by the java compiler into Byte Codes which are secure and portable across different platforms . these byte codes are essentially instructions encapsulated in single type, to what is known as a java virtual machine (JVM) which resides in standard browser. Jvm verifies these byte codes when downloaded by the browser for integrity. Jvms available for almost all OS. JVM converts these byte codes into machine specific instructions at runtime.

FEATURES OF JAVA

- java is object-oriented language and supports encapsulation, inheritance , polymorphism and dynamic binding , but does not support multiple inheritance. every thing in java is an object except some primitive datatypes .
- java is portable architecture neutral that is java programs once compiled can be executed on any machine that is enabled.
- JAVA is distributed in its approach and used for internet programming.
- Java is robust, secured, high performing and dynamic in nature.
- Java supports multithreading. There for different parts of the program can be executed at the same time

JAVA AND INTERNET

Java is strongly associated with internet and known as internet programming language. Internet users can use java to create applet programs and run them locally using java enabled browser search as hot java. Applets can be downloaded from remote machine via internet and run it on local machine .

JAVA AND WORLD WIDE WEB

World wide web is an open ended information retrieval system designed to be used in the distributed environment. This system contains web pages that provide both information and controls. We can navigate to a new web page in any direction. This is made possible with HTML java was meant to be used in distributed environment such as internet. So java could be easily incorporated into the web system and is capable of supporting animation graphics , games and other special effect. The web has become more dynamic and interactive with support of java. We can run a java program on remote machine over internet with the support of web .

JAVA ENVIRONMENT

Java environment includes a large no.of tools which are part of the system known as java development kit (JDK) and hundreds of classes, methods, and interfaces grouped into packages forms part of java standard library(JSL).

JAVA ARCHITECTURE

Java architecture provides a portable , robust , high performing environment for development. Java provides portability by compiling the byte codes for the java virtual machine which are then interpreted on each platform by the runtime environment . java also provides stringent compile and runtime checking and automatic memory management in order to ensure solid code .

JAVA VIRTUAL MACHINE

When we compile the code, java compiler creates machine code (byte code) for a hypothetical machine called java virtual machine (jvm). The jvm will execute the byte code and overcomes the issue of portability . the code is written and compile for one machine and interpreted all other machines . this machine is called java virtual machine .

PARADIGM OF JAVA

- Dynamic down loading applets(small application programs);
- Elimination of flatware phenomenon that is providing those features of a product that user needs at a time. The remaining features of a product can remain in the server.
- Changing economic model of the software
- Up-to-date software availability

- Supports network entire computing
- Supports CORBA & DCOM

ABOUT HTML

HTML (hyper text markup language) is a language used to create hyper text documents that have hyper links embedded in them . it consists of tags embedded in the text of a document with HTML. We can build web pages or web documents. it is basically a formatting language and not a programming language. The browser reading the document interprets mark up tags to help format the document for subsequent display to a reader.

HTML is a language for describing structured documents. HTML is a platform independent. WWW(world wide web) pages are written using HTML. HTML tags control in part the representation of the WWW page when view with web browser. The browser interpretes HTML tags in the web document and displays it. Different browsers show data differently. Examples of browsers used to be web pages include:

- Netscape
- Internet Explorer

JAVA SCRIPT

Java script is a general purpose , prototype based , object oriented scripting language developed jointly by sun and netscape and is meant for the WWW . it is designed to be embedded in diverse applications and systems , with out consuming much memory . java script borrows most of its syntax from java but also inherits from awk and perl , with some indirect influence from self in its object prototype system.

Java scripts dynamically typed that is programs donot declare variable types, and the type of variable is unrestricted and can change at runtime . source can be generated at run time and evaluated against an arbitrary scope. Typical implementations compile by translating source into a specified byte code format, to check syntax and source consistency. Note that the availability to generate and interpret programs at runtime implies the presence of a compiler at runtime.

Java script is a high level scripting language that does not depend on or expose particular machine representations or operating system services. It provides automatic storage management, typically using a garbage collector.

FEATURES:

- Java script is embedded into HTML documents and is executed with in them.
- Java script is browser dependent
- Javascript is an interpreted language that can be interpreted by the browser at run time .
- Java script is loosely typed language
- Java script is an object based language.
- Java script is an Event-Driven language and supports event handlers to specify the functionality of a button.

ADVANTAGES

1. java script can be used for client side application
2. java script provides means to contain multiframe windows for presentation of the web.
3. java script provides basic data validation before it is sent to the server. Eg : login and password checking or whether the values entered are correct or whether all fields in a form are filled and reduced network traffic
4. it creates interactive forms and client side lookup tables .

ORACLE

INTRODUCTION:

Oracle is a relational database management system, which organizes data in the form of tables. Oracle is one of many database servers based on RDBMS model, which manages a sea of data that attends three specific things-data structures, data integrity and data manipulation. With oracle cooperative server technology we can realize the benefits of open, relational systems for all the applications. Oracle makes efficient use of all systems resources, on all hardware architecture; to deliver unmatched performance, price performance and scalability. Any DBMS to be called as RDBMS has to satisfy Dr.E.F.Codd's rules.

DISTINCT FEATURES OF ORACLE:

- **ORACLE IS PORTABLE:**

The Oracle RDBMS is available on wide range of platforms ranging from PCs to super computers and as a multi user loadable module for Novel NetWare, if you develop application on system you can run the same application on other systems without any modifications.

- **ORACLE IS COMPATIBLE:**

Oracle commands can be used for communicating with IBM DB2 mainframe RDBMS that is different from Oracle, that is Oracle compatible with DB2. Oracle RDBMS is a high performance fault tolerant DBMS, which is specially designed for online transaction processing and for handling large database applications.

JDBC DRIVERS:

The JDBC API only defines interfaces for objects used for performing various database-related tasks like opening and closing connections, executing SQL commands, and retrieving the results. We all write our programs to interfaces and not

implementations. Either the resource manager vendor or a third party provides the implementation classes for the standard JDBC interfaces. These software implementations are called JDBC drivers. JDBC drivers transform the standard JDBC calls to the external resource manager-specific API calls. The diagram below depicts how a database client written in java accesses an external resource manager using the JDBC API and JDBC driver:

Depending on the mechanism of implementation, JDBC drivers are broadly classified into four types.

TYPE1:

Type1 JDBC drivers implement the JDBC API on top of a lower level API like ODBC. These drivers are not generally portable because of the independency on native libraries. These drivers translate the JDBC calls to ODBC calls and ODBC sends the request to external data source using native library calls. The JDBC-ODBC driver that comes with the software distribution for J2SE is an example of a type1 driver.

TYPE2:

Type2 drivers are written in mixture of java and native code. Type2 drivers use vendors specific native APIs for accessing the data source. These drivers transform the JDBC calls to vendor specific calls using the vendor's native library.

These drivers are also not portable like type1 drivers because of the dependency on native code.

TYPE3:

Type3 drivers use an intermediate middleware server for accessing the external data sources. The calls to the middleware server are database independent. However, the middleware server makes vendor specific native calls for accessing the data source. In this case, the driver is purely written in java.

TYPE4:

Type4 drivers are written in pure java and implement the JDBC interfaces and translate the JDBC specific calls to vendor specific access calls. They implement the data transfer and network protocol for the target resource manager. Most of the leading database vendors provide type4 drivers for accessing their database servers.

DRIVER MANAGER AND DRIVER:

The `java.sql` package defines an interface called `Java.sql.Driver` that makes to be implemented by all the JDBC drivers and a class called `java.sql.DriverManager` that acts as the interface to the database clients for performing tasks like connecting to external resource managers, and setting log streams. When a JDBC client requests the `DriverManager` to make a connection to an external resource manager, it delegates the task to an appropriate driver class implemented by the JDBC driver provided either by the resource manager vendor or a third party.

JAVA.SQL.DRIVERMANAGER:

The primary task of the class driver manager is to manage the various JDBC drivers register. It also provides methods for:

- Getting connections to the databases.
- Managing JDBC logs.
- Setting login timeout.

MANAGING DRIVERS:

JDBC clients specify the JDBC URL when they request a connection. The driver manager can find a driver that matches the request URL from the list of register drivers and delegate the connection request to that driver if it finds a match JDBC URLs normally take the following format:

<protocol>:<sub-protocol>:<resource>

The protocol is always jdbc and the sub-protocol and resource depend on the type of resource manager. The URL for postgresSQL is in the format:

Jdbc: postgres ://< host> :< port>/<database>

Here host is the host address on which post master is running and database is the name of the database to which the client wishes to connect.

MANAGING CONNECTION:

DriverManager class is responsible for managing connections to the databases:

```
public static Connection getConnection (String url,Properties info) throws  
SQLException
```

This method gets a connection to the database by the specified JDBC URL using the specified username and password. This method throws an instance of SQLException if a database access error occurs.

CONNECTIONS:

The interface `java.sql.Connection` defines the methods required for a persistent connection to the database. The JDBC driver vendor implements this interface. A database 'vendor-neutral' client never uses the implementation class and will always use only the interface. This interface defines methods for the following tasks:

- Statements, prepared statements, and callable statements are the different types of statements for issuing sql statements to the database by the JDBC clients.
- For getting and setting auto-commit mode.
- Getting meta information about the database.
- Committing and rolling back transactions.

CREATING STATEMENTS:

The interface `java.sql.Connection` defines a set of methods for creating database statements. Database statements are used for sending SQL statements to the database:

Public Statement `createStatement ()` throws `SQLException`

This method is used for creating instances of the interface `java.sql.Statement`. This interface can be used for sending SQL statements to the database. The interface `java.sql.Statement` is normally used for sending SQL statements that don't take any arguments. This method throws an instance of `SQLException` if a database access error occur:

Public Statement `createStatement (int resType, int resConcurrency)` throws `SQLException`

JDBC RESULTSETS:

A JDBC resultset represents a two dimensional array of data produced as a result of executing SQL `SELECT` statements against databases using JDBC statements. JDBC resultsets are represented by the interface `java.sql.ResultSet`. The JDBC vendor provider provides the implementation class for this interface.

SCROLLING RESULTSETS:

public boolean next() throws SQLException

public boolean previous() throws SQLException

public boolean first() throws SQLException

public boolean last() throws SQLException

ACCESSING RESULTSET DATA:

Method name and Purpose	
public boolean getBoolean (int i)	
Gets the data in the specified column as a boolean.	
public boolean getBoolean (String col)	
public int getInt(int I)	Gets the data in the specied columnas an int.
public int getInt (String col)	
public String getString (int I)	Gets the data in the specied column as a string.
Public String getString (String col)	

STATEMENT:

The interface java.sql.Stament is normally used for sending SQL statements that do not have IN or OUT parameters. The JDBC driver vendor provides the implementation class for this interface. The common methods required by the different JDBC statements are defined in this interface. The methods defined by java.sql. Statement can be broadly categorized as follows:

- Executing SQL statements
- Querying results and resultsets
- Handling SQL batches
- Other miscellaneous methods

The interface `java.sql.statement` defines methods for executing different SQL statements like `SELECT`, `UPDATE`, `INSERT`, `DELETE`, and `CREATE`.

Public `ResultSet` execute Query (string sql) throws `SQLException`

The following figure shows how the `DriverManager`, `Driver`, `Connection`, `Statement`, `ResultSet` classes are connected.

JAVA SERVER PAGES (JSP)

INTRODUCTION:

Java Server Pages (JSP) technology enables you to mix regular, static HTML with dynamically generated content. You simply write the regular HTML in the normal manner, using familiar Web-page-building tools. You then enclose the code for the dynamic parts in special tags, most of which start with `<%` and end with `%>`.

THE NEED FOR JSP:

Servlets are indeed useful, and JSP by no means makes them obsolete. However,

- It is hard to write and maintain the HTML.
- You cannot use standard HTML tools.
- The HTML is inaccessible to non-Java developers.

BENEFITS OF JSP:

JSP provides the following benefits over servlets alone:

- It is easier to write and maintain the HTML: In this no extra backslashes, no double quotes, and no lurking Java syntax.
- You can use standard Web-site development tools:

We use Macromedia Dreamweaver for most of the JSP pages. Even HTML tools that know nothing about JSP can be used because they simply ignore the JSP tags.

- You can divide up your development team:

The Java programmers can work on the dynamic code. The Web developers can concentrate on the representation layer. On large projects, this division is very important. Depending on the size of your team and the complexity of your project, you can enforce a weaker or stronger separation between the static HTML and the dynamic content.

CREATING TEMPLATE TEXT:

A large percentage of our JSP document consists of static text known as template text. In almost all respects, this HTML looks just like normal HTML follows all the same syntax rules, and simply “passed through” to that client by the servlet created to handle the page. Not only does the HTML look normal, it can be created by whatever tools you already are using for building Web pages.

There are two minor exceptions to the “template text passed through” rule. First, if you want to have `<% Or %>` in the output, you need to put `<\<% or %\>` in the template text. Second, if you want a comment to appear in the JSP page but not in the resultant document,

```
<%-- JSP Comment -- %>
```

HTML comments of the form:

```
<!--HTML Comment -->
```

are passed through to the client normally.

TYPES OF JSP SCRIPTING ELEMENTS:

JSP scripting elements allow you to insert Java code into the servlet that will be generated from the JSP page. There are three forms:

1. **Expressions** of the form `<%=Java Expression %>`, which are evaluated and inserted into the servlet’s output.
2. **Scriptlets** of the form `<%Java code %>`, which are inserted into the servlet’s `_jspService` method (called by service).
3. **Declarations** of the form `<%! Field/Method Declaration %>`, which are inserted into the body of the servlet class, outside any existing methods.

USING JSP EXPRESSIONS:

A JSP element is used to insert values directly into the output. It has the following form:

```
<%= Java Expression %>
```

The expression is evaluated, converted to a string, and inserted in the page. This evaluation is performed at runtime (when the page is requested) and thus has full access to the information about the request. For example, the following shows the date/time that the page was requested.

```
Current time: <%=new java.util.Date () %>
```

PREDEFINED VARIABLES:

To simplify expressions we can use a number of predefined variables (or “implicit objects”). The specialty of these variables is that, the system simply tells what names it will use for the local variables in `_jspService`. The most important ones of these are:

- **request**, the `HttpServletRequest`.
- **response**, the `HttpServletResponse`.
- **session**, the `HttpSession` associated with the request
- **out**, the writer used to send output to clients.
- **application**, the `ServletContext`. This is a data structure shared by all servlets and JSP pages in the web application and is good for storing shared data.

Here is an example:

```
Your hostname: <%= request.getRemoteHost () %>
```

COMPARING SERVLETS TO JSP PAGES

JSP works best when the structure of the HTML page is fixed but the values at various places need to be computed dynamically. If the structure of the page is dynamic, JSP is less beneficial. Some times servlets are better in such a case. If the page consists of binary data or has little static content, servlets are clearly superior. Sometimes the answer is neither servlets nor JSP alone, but rather a combination of both.

WRITING SCRIPTLETS

If you want to do something more complex than output the value of a simple expression .JSP scriptlets let you insert arbitrary code into the servlet’s `_jspService` method. Scriptlets have the following form:

```
<% Java code %>
```

Scriptlets have access to the same automatically defined variables as do expressions (request, response, session, out , etc) .So for example you want to explicitly send output of the resultant page , you could use the out variable , as in the following example:

```
<%  
    String queryData = request.getQueryString ();  
    out.println (“Attached GET data: “+ queryData);  
%>
```

SCRIPTLET EXAMPLE:

As an example of code that is too complex for a JSP expression alone, a JSP page that uses the `bgColor` request parameter to set the background color of the page .Simply using

```
<BODY BGCOLOR="<%= request.getParameter ("bgcolor") %>" %>
```

would violate the cardinal rule of reading form data.

USING DECLARATIONS

A JSP declaration lets you define methods or fields that get inserted into the main body of the servlet class .A declaration has the following form:

```
<%! Field or Method Definition %>
```

Since declarations do not generate output, they are normally used in conjunction with JSP expressions or scriptlets. In principle, JSP declarations can contain field (instance variable) definitions, method definitions, inner class definitions, or even static initializer blocks: anything that is legal to put inside a class definition but outside any existing methods. In practice declarations almost always contain field or method definitions.

We should not use JSP declarations to override the standard servlet life cycle methods. The servlet into which the JSP page gets translated already makes use of these methods. There is no need for declarations to gain access to `service`, `doGet`, or `doPost`, since calls to `service` are automatically dispatched to `_jspService` , which is where code resulting from expressions and scriptlets is put. However for initialization and cleanup, we can use `jspInit` and `jspDestroy`- the standard `init` and `destroy` methods are guaranteed to call these methods in the servlets that come from JSP.

JAKARTA TOMCAT

Tomcat is the Servlet/JSP container. Tomcat implements the Servlet 2.4 and JavaServer Pages 2.0 specification. It also includes many additional features that make it a useful platform for developing and deploying web applications and web services.

TERMINOLOGY:

Context – a Context is a web application.

`$CATALINA_HOME` – This represents the root of Tomcat installation.

DIRECTORIES AND FILES:

/bin – Startup, shutdown, and other scripts. The *.sh files (for Unix systems) are functional duplicates of the *.bat files (for Windows systems). Since the Win32 command-line lacks certain functionality, there are some additional files in here.

/conf – Configuration files and related DTDs. The most important file in here is server.xml. It is the main configuration file for the container.

/logs – Log files are here by default.

/webapps – This is where webapps go\

INSTALLATION:

Tomcat will operate under any Java Development Kit (JDK) environment that provides a JDK 1.2 (also known as Java2 Standard Edition, or J2SE) or later platform.

JDK is needed so that servlets, other classes, and JSP pages can be compiled.

DEPLOYMENT DIRECTORIES FOR DEFAULT WEB APPLICATION:

HTML and JSP Files

- Main Location
\$CATALINA_HOME/webapps/ROOT
- Corresponding URLs.
<http://host/SomeFile.html>
<http://host/SomeFile.jsp>
- More Specific Location (Arbitrary Subdirectory).
\$CATALINA_HOME/webapps/ROOT/SomeDirectory
- Corresponding URLs
<http://host/SomeDirectory/SomeFile.html>
<http://host/SomeDirectory/SomeFile.jsp>

Individual Servlet and Utility Class Files

- Main Location (Classes without Packages).
\$CATALINA_HOME/webapps/ROOT/WEB-INF/classes
- Corresponding URL (Servlets).
<http://host/servlet/ServletName>

- More Specific Location (Classes in Packages).
\$CATALINA_HOME/webapps/ROOT/WEB-INF/classes/packageName
- Corresponding URL (Servlets in Packages).
<http://host/servlet/packageName.ServletName>

Servlet and Utility Class Files Bundled in JAR Files

- Location
\$CATALINA_HOME/webapps/ROOT/WEB-INF/lib
- Corresponding URLs (Servlets)
<http://host/servlet/ServletName>
<http://host/servlet/packageName.ServletName>

5. TESTING AND IMPLEMENTATION

Testing plays a critical role for quality assurance and for ensuring the reliability of the software. Its basic function is to detect the errors. After the coding phase, testing is done to test the proper working of the new system. Testing is the process of executing a program with the intention of finding errors. It is a complete verification to determine whether the objectives are met and the user requirements are satisfied. The testing phase involves testing of a system using various test data. Preparation of the test data plays a vital role in the system testing. After preparing the test data, the system under study is testing using those test data. Errors were found and corrected by using the following testing steps and corrections are recorded for future references. Thus, a series of testing is performed on the system before it is ready for coding. Since code is the only product that can be executed frequently whose actual behavior can be observed, this phase is so important for the successful implementation of the software product. Thus, the goal of testing is to uncover the requirements, design and coding errors in the program.

5.1 Unit Testing

The first step in the testing is the unit testing. Unit test is normally considered as an adjunct to the coding step. After the coding has been developed, received and verified for correct syntax, unit testing begins. The standalone modules were tested individually for their correct functionality, with the corresponding data. This ensures the reliability of the modules when integrated. Each and every module is tested independently with sample data and it was found that all modules are properly functioning. Using the unit test plans, prepared in the design phase of the system as a guide, important control paths are tested to uncover errors within the boundary of the modules. Boundary conditions were checked, all independent paths were exercised to ensure that all statements in the module are checked at least once and all error handling paths were tested. Each unit was thoroughly tested to check if it might fall in any possible situation. This testing was carried out during the programming itself. At the end of this testing phase, each unit was found to be working satisfactory, as regard to the expected output from the module.

5.2 Integration Testing

The second step in the testing process is the Integration testing. Integration testing is the systematic technique for constructing the program structure while conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. All the modules when unit testing will work properly but after interfacing the data can be lost across an interface, one module can have an inadvertent, adverse effect on other, sub functions when combined may not produce the desired major function, global data structures can cause problems, etc.

Integration testing was performed by integrating all the individual modules and the activities of the user such as loading layers, retrieving information from any functions applying themes based on the records present in the database etc. and is found that it works good to the examination of the end users. Hence, the objective of integration testing is to take unit tested modules and build a final program structure.

All the modules developed are independent. Even the whole process of approval for all. Each module is integrated well with other modules. And all the interfaces are tested successfully.

5.3 Functional Testing

This test involves testing the system under typical operating conditions with sample input values. Functional testing was performed on the system by giving existing industry id or plot number and a null or string as the input for any field in which case the user should be redirected to the same state with the appropriate message, rather than proceeding and crashing in the system.

Functional testing was performed on the system by raising the demand with an eye to check all the validations. The total processing of the system is satisfactory with the following results.

- All the validations are clearly notified to the user regarding jobseekers reg, new client reg, job order, job providers, and job search preparation etc.
- Almost all the functional errors, data storage errors and all types of logical errors are tested successfully.

5.4 Acceptance Testing

User acceptance test of a system is the factor for the success of the system. The system under consideration was listed for user acceptance by keeping constant touch with the perspective user of the system at the time of design, development and making changes whenever required for unit testing.

The requirements of the customer are gathered at regular intervals at the developing site itself. The problems that are to be visualized through this tool are been gathered by the customer and are reported.

The user at the user's site carried this test. Live data entered and the system's output was compared with what was manually prepared. Here the system has met the user's requirement in the following fields:

- Data Entry
- Error Handling
- Reporting and corrections
- Data Access Protections
- System Output

5.5 Implementation

Implementation includes all those activities that take place to convert the old system to the new system .The new system will replace he existing system. The aspects of implementation are as follows.

Conversion, Post Implementation Review.

Conversion

Conversion means changing from one system to another. The objective is to put the tested system into operation. It involves proper installation of the software package developed and training the operating staff.

The software has been installed and found to be functioning properly. The users how to be trained to handle the system effectively. Sample data provide to the operating stuff and were asked to operate on the system. The operating stuffs now have a clear out look of the software and are ready for practical implementation of the package.

Post Implementation Review

A post implantation review is an evaluation of system in terms of the extent to which the system accomplishes the started objectives. This starts after the system is implemented and conversation is complete.

6. CONCLUSION AND ENHANCEMENTS

6.1 Conclusion

This system has been developed successfully incorporate all the requirements. Appropriate care has taken during database design maintain database integrity and to avoid redundancy of data. This site was developed in such a way that any further modifications needed can be easily done. User feels freely while using this site. In this all technical complexities are hidden. This site is a more user friendly.

The quality features like correctness, efficiency, usability, maintainability, portability, accuracy, errors free, tolerance, expandability and communicatively all are successfully done.

Foreseeable enhancements

There is always a room for improvement in any software package, however good and efficient it may be. The important thing is that the website should be flexible enough for further modifications. Considering this important factor, the web site is designed in such a way that the provisions are given for further enhancements. At present this website provides all the information using static pages and reservation forms.

In future we can enhance our project by providing options like.

Include many sites information.

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8. APPENDICES

8.1 Appendix A

Core Technologies in J2EE:

- **Java Servlet Technology** - Servlets are platform-independent, 100% pure Java server-side modules that fit seamlessly into a web server framework and can be used to extend the capabilities of a web server with minimal overhead, maintenance, and support
- **JDBC (Java Database Connectivity)** - Provides a uniform interface to a wide range of relational databases, and provides a common base on which higher-level tools and interfaces can be built.

JMS (Java Mail Service)

The Multi tier architecture

Client / Presentation tier

JavaScript

Generally a thin Client is preferred in a Web application. This is because this layer travels across the networks in the Internet & serves the pages in the client web browser. If the amount of data that goes into this layer is great, it takes more time to go across the Internet. The response time from the server will be increased. So to maintain a thin client a two pronged strategy is used.

The first one is to check for client side validations in the browser itself. The second one is that any considerable interactions or data required on the server are stored or cached in JavaBeans or Enterprise JavaBeans(Stateful Session Beans) or classes on the Server itself & only data that is to be shown in the browser is sent across to the browser. To achieve the first objective JavaScript is the best solution available.

The best example that can be given is if in a login page the user presses the login button without entering any text for either the user name or password fields, it will be a waste of time to go back to the server & check for validations there. JavaScript has been used in these situations, which will check for the validations on the client browser & save a lot of time being wasted.

JavaScript was developed by Netscape & is modeled very closely on the Java language. This makes it a natural choice to complement JSP for the development of the client tier. The reference Manual of JavaScript [JS-NET], has been referred to extensively while using JavaScript in the Project.

Business Logic Tier

The Business logic tier comprises a whole set of Java classes .

Internet Services

For access to Internet services, J2EE supports the HTTP, TCP/IP, and SSL protocols.

- TCP/IP (Transport Control Protocol over Internet Protocol) provides a mechanism to establish connections and reliably deliver streams of data between Internet hosts.
- HTTP (HyperText Transfer Protocol) is the basis of Internet browsers and Web servers. A client makes an HTTP request to a server, and HTML hypertext is returned via HTTP.
- SSL (Secure Socket Layer) provides a secure mechanism for clients to access hosts on the Internet, without someone tampering or accessing the messages. In addition, new extensible Markup Language (XML) functionality is supported in J2EE 1.3. XML provides tagged data similar to HTML, but the tags describe the data rather than the way the data is displayed. XML can be used to transfer formatted data between applications or servers on the Internet—for example, for supporting transactions between businesses (B2B). Support for parsing XML and representing XML as objects is implemented and is being currently standardized.

Application Configurations Supported by the J2EE Architecture

The J2EE architecture can be used to configure various multitier applications. In a typical multitier Web application, a Web server implemented using JSP or servlets sends HTML or XML to a Web browser client. It generates dynamic content by making calls to database systems or existing enterprise services using JNDI, JDBC, JavaIDL, and other J2EE supported technologies (see Figure below - Multitier Application with Web Server/JSP Interface and EJB Middle Tier).

A multitier J2EE application uses Web components and accesses multiple databases, with Enterprise JavaBeans in between to encapsulate more complex business logic than could be supported in JSP alone (see Figure below - Multitier Application with Web Server/JSP Interface and EJB Middle Tier). EJBs also automate the transaction monitoring required to access multiple databases.

Data Storage Tier

The best way to store data is in a Relational database. There has been a lot of development in the databases & they have evolved from storing the data on punch cards, through storage in flat files, & through storage in simple databases to storage in Relational databases. The most successful commercial databases are relational databases.

Recently a lot of research is taking place on Object oriented databases because they are supposed to overcome the disadvantages of relational databases. Though there are some implementations of Object oriented databases like O2, the commercial industry has still not adopted it in any significant way. Most of the commercial applications use relational databases to store the persistent data. In view of this the best option to store persistent data for the application is a Relational Database system.

JDBC (Java Database Connectivity)

The JDBC interface is a pure Java API used to execute SQL statements. The JDBC provides a set of classes and interfaces that can be used by developers to write database applications. It can be broken down into four steps.

- Open a Connection to the Database.
- Execute a SQL statement.
- Process the results.
- Close the connection to the database.

The JDBC provides support for two and three-tier database access models.

If you use the two-tier database access model, your Java application talks directly to the database. The results of these commands are then sent back from the database directly to the application.

When you use three-tier model, your JDBC sends commands to a middle-tier, which in turn sends commands to the database. The results of these commands are then sent back to the middle-tier, which communicates them to the application.

JDBC Driver Types

- JDBC-ODBC Bridge, plus ODBC Driver
- Native-API, Partly- Java Driver
- JDBC-Net, Pure Java Driver
- Native-Protocol, pure Java Driver

JDBC-ODBC Bridge

It provides JDBC access to databases through ODBC drivers. The ODBC driver must be configured on the client for the bridge to work.

Native-API

The native-API driver converts JDBC commands into DBMS-specific native calls. The client must have some binary code loaded on its machine.

JDBC-Net, Pure Java Driver

The JDBC-Net drivers are a three-tier solution. This type of driver translates JDBC calls into a database-independent network protocol that is sent to a middleware server. This server then translates this DBMS-independent protocol into a DBMS-specific protocol, which is sent to a particular database.

Native-Protocol, pure Java Driver

These drivers are pure Java drivers that communicate directly with the vendor's database. They do this by converting JDBC commands directly into the database engine's native protocol.

8.2 Appendix B

Introduction to Oracle8.0

Oracle is a Comprehensive Operating Environment that packs the power of mainframe Relational database Management system into users microcomputers. It provides a set of functional programs that user can use as tools to build structures and perform tasks, because *applications* developed in oracle are completely portable to other versions of the programmer who can create a complex application in a single user environment and then move it to a multi user platform. Users do not have to be an expert to appreciate Oracle but, the better user understands the programs, the productively, creatively he can use the tools it provides.

Why Oracle?

I selected Oracle for developing the project work because it supports RDBMS features. Also it provides tools like SQL * PLUS, SQL*FORMS, SQL*REPORT WRITER, SQL*MENUS. Also it supports high security to the Data and faster Accessing capability.

It can be run on a variety of platforms and Operating systems. It provides Host language procedures like PRO*C, PRO*COBOL. An application that requires many lines of Host language code can be developed very easily. One can develop an Application easily by providing User-friendly Environment Support for Codd's Rules:

Oracle supports the following rules of **Dr.E.F.CODD**:

Rule1: Information Rule (Representation of information)

Rule 2: Guaranteed Access

Rule3: Systematic Representation of missing Information

Rule 4: Comprehensive On Line Catalogue

Rule 5: Comprehensive Data Sub-Language

Rule 6: View Updating

Rule 7: High Level Insert, Update, Delete

Rule 8: Physical Data Independence

Rule 9: Logical Data Independence

Rule 10: Integrity Independence

Rule 11: Distribution Dependence

Rule 12: Non-Subversion

FEATURES OF ORACLE

Oracle is portable

The Oracle RDBMS is available on wide range of platforms, ranging from PCs to super computers and as a multi-user network loadable module (NLM) for Novell Netware. If you develop an application on one system you can run the same application on other systems without any modifications.

Oracle is Compatible

The Oracle command can be used for communicating with IBM, DB/2, Mainframe RDBMS, which is different from Oracle, i.e., Oracle is compatible with DB/2. Oracle is a high performance fault tolerant DBMS which is specially designed for on-line transaction processing and for handling the large database applications.

Oracle RDBMS is available with 2 options

Oracle RDBMS version 8.0 with transaction processing option and Oracle RDBMS version 8.0 without transaction processing option. Oracle is very high level of transaction processing, throughout, which is as follows:

- The Row Level Lock Manager
- PL/SQL a procedural language extension of SQL
- Forms 5.0

Oracle Tools

Oracle is RDBMS, which stores and displays the Data in the form of tables. A table consists of rows and columns. A single row is called Record. Oracle is a modular system that contains Oracle Database (DB Manager) and several Tools (Functional Programs).

Oracle Tools do 4 major kinds of work

- Database management
- Data access and manipulation
- Programming
- Connectivity.

Data Access and Manipulation Tools:

These are the tools used for communication with database manger for data access and manipulation. These tools can be used for not only access and manipulation but you can use design or use an application. Each tool Provides separate entry point and a unique approach to the Oracle system. The tools are firmly based on ANSI standard SQL.

SQL*PLUS

SQL* Plus is direct access to the Oracle RDBMS. You can see SQL commands to define, control and manipulate and query data. All users like DBA's, high-level system developers and others can talk straight in Oracle RDBMS.

Connectivity Tools

The connectivity tools help in connecting the Oracle databases through network and to other database systems. SQL* Plus allows for accessing the IBM, DB/2 (an IBM Mainframe RDBMS) and SQL/DS (Structured query language for data system) databases directly using the normal Oracle commands without doing any modifications.

SQL

The name SQL stands for structure query language. SQL is data access language, like any other language, it is used for communication. SQL communicates with database manager. The database manager could be Oracle, DB2, and SQL base, in grace or any RDBMS that supports SQL language. These database systems understand SQL.

SQL is easy to learn. Despite the fact that the SQL is a computer programming language, it is much simpler than traditional programming language like COBOL, BASIC, FORTRAN or APL. This is due to the fact that SQL is non-procedural language.

Features of SQL

SQL users a free form (A non mathematical syntax), English like structure for its commands.

Ex: You select some data from your table, where certain conditions are met, you insert your values into some table; you delete data from some table where conditions are met. It is very logical and easy to follow.

SQL decides how it gets your data to and from database. All you have to specify is what and SQL does the rest. This is being called non navigational and it promises large productivity gains for the data processing identity. Sometimes programs in traditional processing system can be replaced with a single SQL query.

1. Most traditional RDBMS support both interactive and static SQL processing i.e. SQL statements can be executed in an alternative fashion where you talk directly to the database manager or SQL statement can be embedded in traditional computer programming language like COBOL. This is necessary because SQL is originally intended to use with other programming language. By itself it has no commands for screen dialogue or for more than crude report formatting. So this dual mode feature is very important in any kind of formal data processing application. The embedded SQL statements themselves are very simple to their interactive counter parts.

2. Finally, SQL process data at the set level, meaning your updates will change a set of records (rows) and query output will comeback in a set of records (a result table)

SQL Processing Capabilities

SQL is composed of a Definition language, a Data manipulation language and a Data control language. These three languages support the complete spectrum of Relational Data processing activity. In fact most SQL based products all access to the data through SQL.

1. Data definition language: DDL allows creation, deletion and modification of data structures for bar system. These structures include tables, databases, and indexes.

Ex: Creation, Drop, Alter.

2. Data Manipulation Language: These commands are used to manipulate the data in tables directly or through views. There are four standard DML statements. They are Delete, Insert, and Update.

3. Data control language: These commands are used to control usage and access of data. The most commonly found one's are Grant and Revoke.

PL/SQL

PL/SQL is an extension to SQL. It allows us to use all the SQL data Manipulation statements including insert, delete, update and select as well as the transaction processing statements Commit, Rollback and save point.

PL/SQL blocks can contain any number of SQL combined with the following:

- Flow of control statements such as IF...THEN...ELSE, EXIT and GOTO.
- Repetition statement such as for loop and while loop.
- Assignment statements such as $x = y + z$ unlike SQL, PL/SQL allows logically group a set of statements and send them to the RDBMS as a single block

Advantages of PL/SQL

PL/SQL is completely portable, high performance Transaction processing language (TPL) that gives us more and better ways to express problems and design database application. Specifically PL/SQL provides

The following advantages

- Procedural Capabilities.
- Improved Performance
- Enhanced Productivity
- Portability
- Integration with the RDBMS.

Procedural capabilities

PL/SQL is a TPL that offers procedural solutions. It supports variable and constant declarations, error handling and a wide variety of useful functions within the same PL/SQL block; we can use SQL and all the PL/SQL extensions.

Improved performance

Without PL/SQL the Oracle RDBMS must Process SQL statements one at a time. Each SQL statement results in another call to be RDBMS and higher performance overhead can become significant when we are issuing many SQL statements in a network environment.

Enhanced Productivity

PL/SQL also brings added functionality to non-procedural tools Such as SQL forms. With PL/SQL in these tools, software developers can use familiar procedural language construct to develop applications.

Portability

Applications written in PL/SQL are portable to any computer hardware and operating system environment running the oracle version 8i RDBMS.

Integration with the RDBMS

Both PL/SQL and Oracle have their foundation in SQL also. Most PL/SQL variable has Data types native to the RDBMS Data Dictionary

Main Features of SQL

SQL Data manipulation statements are built into PL/SQL. This allows inserting new data into a database, retrieving, modifying and deleting data.

Support for SQL

By extending SQL, PL/SQL offers a unique combination of power and ease of use. We can access our Oracle database and manipulate its data flexibly and safely because PL/SQL supports SQL DML statements, SQL TPL statements, SQL functions and SQL predicates. SQL data definition statements such as Alter, Create and Rename and data control statements connect; Grant and Revoke statements are supported.

SQL Data Manipulation Statements:

A transaction is a sequence of SQL statements that Oracle treats as a unit, so that all changes brought about by the statements are made permanent or undone for the same time. The consistency of the database PL/SQL lets you use the Commit, Rollback and Save point statements. The Commit statement makes permanent any changes made during the current transaction until you commit your changes, other users cannot see them. The Rollback statement ends the current transaction and undoes any changes made since the transaction began. The Save point statement marks the current point in the processing of a transaction.

8.3 Appendix C

Glossary

HTML Element:

Commonly referred as a tag, it is a component of hierarchical structure, defined by a document type definition.

Browser:

Client software for displaying web pages and using hyperlinks to navigate the web.

Common Gateway Interface:

The interface between the browser and server.

Client:

A combination of computer and software capable of receiving information and instruction from a remote host computer or server.

File Transfer Protocol:

The method for remote logging to a computer to exchange the files over a TCP/IP network.

From:HTML Components that enables web author to have input fields on the pages, permitting feedback from users and offering interactive options.

Frames: A Kind of simultaneously hypertext. Present information as currently display group of pages.

Head:Part of a computer documents containing the information about the documents it self.

Hyperlink:

A connection between one file and another file or tin side the file.

Images:

Originally created to include the visual images on pages.

Uniform Resource Locator:

The path to specific document on the internet that consists of protocols, a domain name or IP address, a directory structure, and the document name.

UML--DIAGRAMS

Class Diagram

E-R Diagrams:-

Job Seeker:-

JOBORDER:-

Use case diagrams:-

Use case diagrams:

Client usecase:

Jobseeker use case:

Admin use case:

Sequence Diagram

Clients sequence:

Jobseekers sequence:

Admin's sequence:

Collaboration diagram for jobseeker:

Clients collaboration Diagram:

DFD'S

NOTATIONS USED IN DATA FLOW DIAGRAMS

The logic dataflow diagrams can be drawn using only four simple notations i.e., special symbols or icons and the annotation that associates them with a specific system. Since the choice of notation we follow, does not affect impede or catalyze the system process; we used three symbols from YOURDON notation and one from Gain and Sarson notation as specified below.

Element References

symbols

Data Flow Process

Process

Data Store

Source or Sink

Description:

Process: describes how input data is converted to output Data

Data Store: Describes the repositories of data in a system

Data Flow: Describes the data flowing between process, Data stores and external entities.

Sources: An external entity causing the origin of data.

Sink: An external entity, which consumes the data.

Context level

0 level

1 level

Jobseeker:-

8.4 Appendix D

Screens:

Home page for Secure mail.

Registration page for secure mail:

Registration Page - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Forward Stop Refresh Home Search Favorites Home Mail Print Address Book Favorites

Address http://localhost:2010/SmailDetection/registerpage.htm

Google Search Share Sidewiki Check Translate AutoFill

SECURE MAIL

[Home](#) **Enter Registration Information**

1.Login Information

User Name*:

Password*:

Confirm Password*:

Secret Question*: What was the name of your first school?

Secret Answer*:

2.Personal Information

First Name*:

Middle Name*:

Last Name*:

Date of Birth*(dd/mm/yyyy):

Email*:

Address Line1*:

Address Line2*:

City*:

State*:

Country*:

Registration page

Secret Answer*:

2.Personal Information

First Name*:

Middle Name*:

Last Name*:

Date of Birth*(dd/mm/yyyy):

Email*:

Address Line1*:

Address Line2*:

City*:

State*:

Country*:

Admin's (krest) login:

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Internet Explorer browser window. The title bar reads "Login Page - Microsoft Internet Explorer". The address bar contains "http://localhost:2010/5mailDetection/". The page features a blue header with the text "SECURE MAIL". Below the header is a graphic of a computer monitor displaying a login form with fields for "Name" (containing "internet"), "Password" (containing "*****"), and a "Login" button. A hand cursor is pointing at the "Login" button. To the right of the graphic, the actual login form is displayed with the following fields and values:

- Userid:
- Password:
- Log in button:
- New User? [Register](#)

Admin has logged in:

Managing (Adding) the keywords:

Inserted the keyword by using manage keywords button:

keywords inserted

Displaying the keywords:

List of blocked mails:

Blocklist - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Address http://localhost:2010/SmalDetection/blocklist.jsp?user=krest@securemail.com

Google Search Share Sidewiki Check Translate AutoFill

krest@securemail.com **SECURE MAIL** [Logout](#)

[Back to Home](#)

MailTo	MailFrom	Subject	Message
xy@securemail.com	xyz@securemail.com	bomb,RDX	RDX

User's(xyz) login :

Login Page - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Address http://localhost:2010/SmalDetection/login.html

Google Search Share Sidewiki Check Translate AutoFill

SECURE MAIL

Userid

Password

New User? [Register](#)

© Secure Mail. All Rights Reserved

User's inbox:

Compose mail page:

http://localhost:2010/SmailDetection/composemail.jsp?user=xyz@securemail.com - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Forward Stop Refresh Home Search Favorites Recycle Bin Mail Print Address Book

Address http://localhost:2010/SmailDetection/composemail.jsp?user=xyz@securemail.com

Google Search + Share Sidewiki Check Translate AutoFill

[Back to Home](#)

To:

Subject:

Body

lets use bomb and RDX.

User's Inbox page:
Blocked mails which are sent from the admin

xyz@securemail.com **SECURE MAIL** [Logout](#)

[Back to Home](#)

MailFrom	Subject	Message
krest@gmail.com	mail-daemon	The mail you had sent consists of suspicious information
krest@gmail.com	mail-daemon	The mail you had sent consists of suspicious information

Sent mail page of the user:

xyz@securemail.com **SECURE MAIL** [Logout](#)

[Back to Home](#)

To	Subject	Body
xy@securemail.com	hi	hello

